

A BROAD CHURCH– THE SOCIAL PROFILE OF GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA

James A Athanasou

Independent Researcher, Sydney, Australia

athanasou@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide a social profile of Greek Orthodox in Australia. It is derived from the national census in 2016. The findings can serve as a benchmark for planning community services on the basis of evidence rather than intuition.

Keywords

Greek Orthodox, Australia. social background, census

I. INTRODUCTION

The study of Greek Orthodox in Australia is a topic that has both theoretical and practical significance but is one on which little academic work has been undertaken. This is despite the fact that Australia is home to one of the largest Greek communities in the world. There have been isolated community studies but no large-scale picture of Greek Orthodox in Australia even though they form part of the seventh largest ethnic group in Australia based on the census in 2016.

In discussion with Greek-Australians, there are many views about the make-up of the Greek Orthodox population in Australia. In part, this may be due to newspaper reports, hearsay or other announcements that are made in good spirit. Also, the perception of one's local community seems to colour ideas about Greek Orthodox throughout Australia. When these well-meaning stereotypes are challenged, they do not appear to have a formal basis.

The information in this report is derived from the national census in 2016 in response to the optional question on one's religion ("What is the person's religion?"). At the same time the Census collected other social information that may be of wider relevance to religion. This report might be read usefully in conjunction with the earlier paper in this series: *Greek Orthodox in Australia – the big picture*.¹ That report documented some basic demographic statistics on Eastern Orthodox and Greek Orthodox in Australia.

II. BACKGROUND

There are 373,589 people in Australia who indicated that they are Greek Orthodox. Possibly there are some who did not answer the question accurately in the Census. For instance, they

may have indicated "Orthodox" or "Christian" instead of "Greek Orthodox". It seems likely that there is some underestimate but this is still the most valid information available on Greek Orthodox in Australia.

The 373,859 who indicated that they were Greek Orthodox are 0.0159 in a population of 23,401,891. At this level the margin of error is very small. There is a 99% level of confidence that the actual number is up to 374,400 and it seems extremely unlikely that the total number of Greek Orthodox is anywhere near even 400,000 or more that some assert. The general point is that these figures provide a reasonable basis for describing the Greek Orthodox population in Australia.

The following sections consider topics such as ancestry, language spoken at home, English proficiency, education, occupation, income and marital or household status.

Figure 1. Parental background of Greek Orthodox.

¹ Athanasou James. (2022). GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA – THE BIG PICTURE. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6913953>

What is the overseas ancestry of Greek Orthodox?

Overwhelmingly, Greek Orthodox in Australia are a migrant community. Whilst this will change over time, only 22% (all percentages rounded) of Greek Orthodox have both parents born in Australia. If one adds those whose father only was born overseas or those whose mother only was born overseas then this rises to 34% as second generation. Figure 1 outlines the parental backgrounds of Greek Orthodox.

Is Greek spoken at home?

The Census assessed familiarity with the Greek language, which is an important component of maintenance of cultural heritage.

In Australia, Greek is spoken at home by 215,506 Greek Orthodox out of a total of 373,589 (i.e., 57%). Of course, this does not show the extent of knowledge of Greek.

Figure 2. English language proficiency.

Are Greek Orthodox proficient in the English language?

Equally important for educational, social and vocational adjustment in Australia is the knowledge of English. A person’s self-assessed proficiency in English was indicated in the Census (“How well does the person speak English?”). This question applied only to those people who spoke a language other than English at home. Amongst Greek Orthodox, 33% speak only English.

For the purposes of this report, it will be assumed that those Greek Orthodox who indicate “not applicable” do not speak another language at home but are proficient in English. This means that 75% of the Greek Orthodox population are very proficient in English.

There are, however, just over 40,000 Greek Orthodox who speak another language at home (probably Greek) and who do not speak English well or do not speak English at all (see Figure 2).

What is the occupational background of Greek Orthodox?

The occupational distribution of Greek Orthodox is not as straightforward as some might imagine. At the outset, occupation was not even applicable for 47% of the Greek Orthodox population in Australia (that is, they were not employed or in the labour force). This compares with 45% for the remainder of the general population

It is true that the 33,337 Greek Orthodox who are professionals are the largest of all the major occupational groups. There are more in this category than any other but there are also 24,603 Greek Orthodox who are managers; 26,627 are clerks; 21,587 are technicians or trade workers; and some 20,480 are sales workers. So, the distribution is fairly uniform across occupational groups.

Figure 3. Occupational distribution of Greek Orthodox in Australia.

Anecdotal accounts imply pride in achieving professional occupational status especially for those from a migrant or disadvantaged background. There might be a view that the children of migrants are high achievers and that there are proportionally more Greek-Australians (and hence Greek Orthodox) in the professional group than the rest of the population. This view is mistaken.

The available evidence points to an overestimate of the number of Greek Orthodox who are professionals. Around 11% of Greek Orthodox are professionals whereas 12% of the remaining general population are professionals.

The proportion across the major occupational group is shown in Figure 3. It tracks fairly closely the same proportions as those in the general population (when those who inadequately described, did not state their occupation, or for whom occupation was not applicable are excluded). As far as professionals from a Greek Orthodox background are concerned there are around 1 in 5 and this is slightly less than the proportion in the overall population.

How is income distributed across the Greek Orthodox?

Income levels are related to occupational status. In the Greek Orthodox population, the median level of income is probably less than imagined. The median was in the range \$26,000-\$33,799 for those 299,368 Greek Orthodox who listed an income level.

The smaller number than the total of 373,859 who indicated that they were Greek Orthodox may reflect those on social security benefits such as aged pensions. Naturally for young children and others there may not be any declared income. The breakdown of incomes of those who are Greek Orthodox is shown in Figure 4 and it appears fairly evenly distributed.

Figure 4. Greek Orthodox income levels.

The median income of Greek Orthodox, which is around \$26,00-\$33,799, is slightly less than for other Christian, Hindu, Judaism or Secular or No religion groups. The group with the largest number in the highest earning category (\$156,000 or

more) is Judaism with 12% compared with 3% for Greek Orthodox. Greek Orthodox with nil or negative income are 10% compared with 17% for Hindu, 18% for Buddhism and 20% for Islam.

What is the educational level of Greek Orthodox?

Educational achievement is also related to occupational pathways and income levels. Again, Greek Orthodox are not as distinguished in the area of education as some might have imagined (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Educational achievement of Greek Orthodox.

The proportion of those with postgraduate degrees (3%) is far lower than those from Hinduism (23%) or Judaism (12%). The proportion of Greek Orthodox with a degree is 14% and again this compares poorly with Hinduism (32%), Judaism (32%), Buddhism (21%), no religion (18%) or Islam (17%).

Amongst Buddhism, other Christian, Hinduism, Islam, Judaism or no religion groups, the Greek Orthodox have the highest proportion (17%) of those with the lowest level of education (i.e., Year 9 and below). This low proportion may reflect the effects of post-war migration.

What do we know about the marital and household status of Greek Orthodox?

The registered marital status of Greek Orthodox for whom this is applicable is mainly married or widowed. Just over a quarter have never married (28%), 7% are widowed, 3% separated. 8% divorced and 54% married.

A substantially greater proportion of Greek Orthodox are married compared to other Australians and fewer are non-married. De facto marriages now make up 8% of social marital status among Greek Orthodox compared to 22% in the remaining population.

III. CONCLUSIONS

There are many potential variations in the profile of any individual Greek Orthodox member in Australia. There is no uniform stereotype or characterisation that fits most people.

There is however a modal type or for want of a better word the most common characterisation and in this section a summary is attempted.

The most typical Greek Orthodox is a minority member of the Australian population. He or she has parents who in all likelihood were born overseas but one in three now have at least one parent who is Australian born. Quite a few Greek Orthodox say that Greek is spoken at home but the quality or standard of the Greek language is not determined. Just on one-third speak only English. There are still some 40,000 who do not speak English at all but over time this number will decline.

The occupational status of Greek Orthodox is remarkably similar to that of the wider Australian population. There are not more professionals among Greek Orthodox than one might expect. Overly high achievement of the second or subsequent generations is a myth.

The educational achievement of Greek Orthodox is well below that of Hinduism, Judaism, Buddhism, no religion or Islam. Furthermore, Greek Orthodox have the highest proportion of those with the lowest level of education amongst these religions

In terms of income, Greek Orthodox are not particularly well-off. The median level of income is close to other religious groups but nowhere near as high as that of Judaism or Hinduism. At the other extreme, Greek Orthodox are much less likely than those in Buddhism, Islam or Hinduism to report nil or negative income.

Around 8% of Greek Orthodox are divorced and de facto marriages make up 8% of social marital status but this is still far less than the remaining population (22%).

What does one make of all these figures? Firstly, they do not characterise any one person. They depict the modal person or the most typical Greek Orthodox.

The statistics describe the social and community landscape for most people. They depict the boundaries within which a Church must operate in its dealings with people. For instance, one in 12 are in de facto social marital status; one in 10 cannot speak English; same-sex couples hardly register on the radar; traditional marriage dominates for the most part; and Greek Orthodox are not highly educated nor particularly wealthy. Any stereotype is open to challenge but it is useful to have this social profile at one's disposal for planning religious services and instruction let alone health, education or welfare services. In

conclusion, it seems reasonable to conclude that Greek Orthodox in Australia is indeed a broad church.

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